

AT3A: Assessing Evidence Integration in Protecting Victoria's Biodiversity 2037 Strategy

ENS5010 – Global Challenges and Sustainability

By Owen Pietersen (36849367)

Words: 1470

AI Acknowledgement: ChatGPT (<https://chat.openai.com>) was used after the initial draft to support ideation related to unit concepts, to check that my work addressed all aspects of the assessment rubric, and to assist with refining language, grammar, and clarity. These interactions focused on improving structure and coherence rather than generating content. All ideas, analysis, and final written material are entirely my own, and no AI-generated text has been copied into the assessment.

Introduction

Biodiversity loss is one of the most significant sustainability challenges of the twenty-first century, with accelerating declines in native species, ecosystem function, and ecosystem resilience observed globally (IPBES, 2019). These trends are driven by land-use change, invasive species, urban development, and anthropogenic climate change, all of which degrade essential ecosystem services such as clean water, food production, and carbon storage (zu Ermgassen et al., 2023). In Victoria, these pressures have contributed to the decline of native vegetation, threatened species, and ecosystem health (zu Ermgassen et al., 2023). Since Victoria's agricultural, tourism, and public health sectors depend on resilient ecosystems, biodiversity loss is also a major social and economic risk. This makes early action essential, as ecological damage can become difficult, costly, or impossible once critical ecological thresholds are crossed (Bansal et al., 2025).

Victoria's main policy response is *Protecting Victoria's Environment – Biodiversity 2037*, released by the Department of Environment, Land, Water and Planning (DELWP) in 2017. The strategy presents biodiversity decline as a statewide environmental, social, and economic challenge, outlining a long-term plan to stop biodiversity decline by 2037. It combines conservation programs, habitat restoration, and engagement with Traditional Owners, scientists, stakeholders, and community groups. In doing so, it prioritises high-value conservation areas, using analytical tools, biodiversity accounting, and offsetting mechanisms to guide decision-making (DELWP, 2017).

This analysis evaluates how effectively scientific evidence is integrated and used in *Biodiversity 2037*. It assesses whether evidence is applied transparently, credibly, and strategically across the policy cycle. It then identifies four areas for improvement and proposes short- and long-term strategies for each. The analysis is guided by *Australia's National Science Statement* (2024), which positions evidence-informed policy and decision-making as a core responsibility of government. It also uses the Research-Integration-Utilisation (RIU) model, which highlights that evidence must be utilised in ways that are effective in policy settings (Zeigermann & Böcher, 2020). Finally, the APS200 Australian Policy Cycle framework is used to assess the quantity and quality of evidence across the policy cycle, specifically across the stages of anticipation, formulation, consultation, adoption, and evaluation (Department of Industry, Innovation, Science, Research and Tertiary Education [DIISRTE], 2012).

Assessment

Biodiversity 2037 clearly intends to use scientific evidence across several stages of the policy cycle, yet the transparency of that evidence remains uneven in the core document. In the anticipation stage, the strategy uses ecological claims to establish biodiversity decline as a major challenge. For example, it states that “Victoria’s biodiversity is still in decline” due to land clearing, invasive species, population growth, and climate change (DELWP, 2017, p. 39). However, the policy provides little empirical detail in the main text to substantiate these claims. Moreover, claims such as “over 50 per cent of the state’s native vegetation [has been] cleared since European settlement” are presented without clear sources or explanation of methods (DELWP, 2017, p. 4). This limits transparency and makes evidence more difficult for readers to assess. Importantly, this does not mean the evidence is absent. Rather, much of the supporting detail for the strategy is in a separate document, which weakens transparency for a general reader accessing the main document alone.

Evidence integration becomes more explicit in the formulation stage, where the strategy refers to tools like the Strategic Management Prospects, Change in Suitable Habitat metrics, and the United Nations System of Environmental Economic Accounting (SEEA). These tools demonstrate the use of modelling, spatial analysis, and environmental accounting in decision-making (DELWP, 2017). However, the strategy also acknowledges that parts of the analysis are “much less developed” and require ongoing refinement, testing, and improvement as new information becomes readily available (DELWP, 2017, p. 53). In practice, this framework relies on expert opinion and assumption-driven modelling to estimate future change, raising significant concerns about bias, verifiability, and the limited use of empirical evidence (DELWP, 2017). Therefore, although the formulation stage is evidence-driven, it is not fully transparent about assumptions and uncertainties.

Four key areas of improvement emerge from this assessment, including two that relate directly to the quantity of evidence used across the policy cycle. First, in the anticipation stage, the strategy provides insufficient empirical detail to support major claims about biodiversity decline, with key statistics presented without clear citations. Second, in the adoption and evaluation stages, there is insufficient outcome evidence to determine whether offsetting practices are actually achieving “no net loss” or “net gain”, and whether the Monitoring, Evaluation, Reporting (MER) framework can yet measure policy effectiveness with confidence, given its dependence on future baseline data and reporting (DELWP, 2017, pp. 51-53). Two further areas relate to the quality and transparency of evidence. First, in the

formulation stage, reliance on assumption-driven modelling weakens confidence in projected outcomes, as these claims are not fully explained, validated, or readily replicable. Second, in the formulation and consultation stages, although stakeholder engagement is clearly visible, there is little evidence of peer review or independent scrutiny of methods, models, or datasets used. Together, these issues reduce transparency, weaken credibility, and limit confidence in the strategy's evidence base.

Strategies to Improve Evidence Integration

Weakness	Short-Term Strategy	Long-Term Strategy
Limited empirical detail and methodological transparency in the anticipation stage.	Use existing relationships with stakeholders and scientists to quickly access credible advice and clarify emerging issues.	Build robust relationships between science advisors and policy departments.
Reliance on assumption-driven modelling in the formulation stage.	Undertake knowledge translation activities to integrate evidence for policy audiences.	Develop strategic plans for information gathering, including consideration of longitudinal data sets, data access, and sharing across departments.
Lack of peer review and methodological transparency in the formulation and consultation stage.	Use established relationships with trusted advisors to commission rapid reviews and mediate or broker contested or competing science advice.	Ensure that both policymakers and science advisors have the skills to understand and communicate the risks and implications of contested science.
Lack of empirical evidence for offsets (adoption) and weak MER framework with no clear indicators (evaluation).	Identify and collect meaningful data from the outset, including relevant scientific indicators.	Build long-term science–policy partnerships and longitudinal data collection to strengthen offset evidence and MER indicators.

Table 1. Strategies to improve evidence integration in Biodiversity 2037

Drawing on APS200, these strategies combine short-term action which could improve evidence use immediately with long-term reforms that strengthen evidence systems over time. In the anticipation stage, the most suitable short-term response is knowledge brokering through existing relationships with stakeholders, scientists, and other trusted knowledge holders. This is relevant because the anticipation stage often involves responding to emerging issues effectively in a short period of time (DIISRTE, 2012). In this context, existing networks can quickly connect policymakers to credible experts who can broker advice on biodiversity risks and priorities, improving policymakers' access to credible evidence (Cvitanovic et al., 2025). However, this strategy is limited because established networks may privilege some voices over others, increasing institutional bias and narrowing the evidence base (Redert & Bursens, 2024). Consequently, the stronger long-term strategy is to strengthen science-policy relationships and build more systematic evidence pathways that support proactive risk identification (Cvitanovic et al., 2025).

In the formulation stage, knowledge translation is a suitable short-term strategy because the immediate problem is that modelling is difficult to interpret and insufficiently explained (Kumar et al., 2025). Kumar et al. (2025) describe this as “participatory modeling”, where policymakers and researchers work collaboratively on policy briefs and workshops to clarify assumptions, uncertainties, and limitations (p. 1). However, these approaches do not solve the limited empirical evidence underpinning the modelling. Therefore, the long-term recommendation is to develop strategic evidence frameworks and invest in empirical data collection to strengthen the evidence base. Over time, this would reduce dependence on expert judgement and render projected biodiversity outcomes more transparent, testable, and credible.

In the formulation and consultation stages, the lack of peer review and methodological transparency requires a different response. In the short term, using established relationships to identify methodological gaps and commission rapid reviews would improve credibility, specifically where technical claims lack clear explanation. Rapid reviews provide time-sensitive evidence for decision-making while remaining transparent about methods and trade-offs to preserve accuracy and reliability. However, they may also increase tension with policy timeframes (Garritty et al., 2021). In the long term, creating a standardised peer review process in policy development and ensuring that policymakers and advisors have the skills to communicate the basic risks and implications of contested science would help ensure frameworks are more consistent and precise.

In the adoption and evaluation stages, identifying and collecting meaningful data from the outset is a rational short-term response, as it improves the ability to assess offset performance and track whether MER indicators can measure policy success. This is important because claims about “no net loss” are weakly supported (DELWP, 2017, pp. 51-53). This aligns with recent studies which illustrate that offset systems often struggle to demonstrate and retain biodiversity gains over the long term, as they face major ecological and institutional challenges (Damiens et al., 2021). Long-term investment in science-policy relationships, data collection, and stronger MER indicators is essential to improve the evidence base. The main limitation of this strategy is that implementing long-term monitoring is expensive and difficult to sustain across policy cycles, given the short-term reality of many policy and governance arrangements (Damiens et al., 2021).

These strategies are relevant because they link each weakness to a specific mechanism and stage of the policy cycle. However, their success depends on sustained funding, institutional commitment, and cross-agency coordination, while ecological uncertainty means evidence may remain incomplete.

Conclusion

Overall, this analysis demonstrates that *Biodiversity 2037* uses scientific evidence across the policy cycle, but not always with sufficient depth, transparency, or consistency. Key weaknesses include limited empirical detail, insufficient outcome evidence, assumption-driven modelling, and weak peer scrutiny. The proposed strategies respond to these gaps by improving evidence access, transparency, and monitoring capacity. Future policy development will depend on stronger evidence integration, clearer evaluation across the full policy cycle, and a greater capacity to ensure that biodiversity outcomes are transparent, contestable, and measurable.

References

- Bansal, P., Durand, R., Kreutzer, M., Kunisch, S., & McGahan, A. M. (2025). Strategy can no longer ignore planetary boundaries: A call for tackling strategy's ecological fallacy. *Journal of Management Studies*, 62(2), 965–985. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joms.13088>
- Coggan, A., Carwardine, J., Fielke, S., & Whitten, S. (2021). Co-creating knowledge in environmental policy development: An analysis of knowledge co-creation in the review of the significant residual impact guidelines for environmental offsets in Queensland, Australia. *Environmental Challenges*, 4, Article 100138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envc.2021.100138>
- Cvitanovic, C., Karcher, D. B., Breen, J., Badullovich, N., Cairney, P., Dalla Pozza, R., Duggan, J., Hoffmann, S., Kelly, R., Meadow, A. M., & Posner, S. (2025). Knowledge brokers at the interface of environmental science and policy: A review of knowledge and research needs. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 163, 103973. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103973>
- Damiens, F. L. P., Backstrom, A., & Gordon, A. (2021). Governing for “no net loss” of biodiversity over the long term: Challenges and pathways forward. *One Earth*, 4(1), 60–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.12.012>
- Department of Environment, Land, Water and Planning. (2017). *Protecting Victoria's environment—Biodiversity 2037*. Victorian Government.
- Department of Industry, Innovation, Science, Research and Tertiary Education. (2012). *APS200 project: The place of science in policy development in the public service*. Australian Government.
- Department of Industry, Science and Resources. (2024). *Australia's National Science Statement*. Australian Government.
- Garritty, C., Gartlehner, G., Nussbaumer-Streit, B., King, V. J., Hamel, C., Kamel, C., Affengruber, L., & Stevens, A. (2021). Cochrane Rapid Reviews Methods Group offers evidence-informed guidance to conduct rapid reviews. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 130, 13–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2020.10.007>
- Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. (2019). *Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services* (E. S. Brondízio, J. Settele, S. Díaz, & H. T. Ngo, Eds.). IPBES.

Kumar, K., Jackson-Smith, D., & Bielicki, J. M. (2025). Evaluating credibility, legitimacy, and salience in a participatory modeling project in the food, energy, water nexus.

Environmental Science & Policy, 173, 104249. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2025.104249>

Redert, B., & Bursens, P. (2024). Understanding bias better: A qualitative exploration of bias in advisory councils of EU agencies. *Political Research Exchange*, 6(1), Article 2306279.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/2474736X.2024.2306279>

Zeigermann, U., & Böcher, M. (2020). Challenges for bridging the gap between knowledge and governance in sustainability policy—The case of OECD “focal points” for policy coherence for development. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 114, 102005.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2019.102005>

zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., Devenish, K., Simmons, B. A., Gordon, A., Jones, J. P. G., Maron, M., Schulte to Bühne, H., Sharma, R., Sonter, L. J., Strange, N., Ward, M., & Bull, J. W.

(2023). Evaluating the impact of biodiversity offsetting on native vegetation. *Global Change Biology*, 29(15), 4397–4411. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16801>